

REVIEW ON HYPERTENSION AND ANTIHYPERTENSIVE DRUGS**Vasave Nimba Bamnya***

Dr. Vedprakash Patil Pharmacy College, Gevrai Tanda, Paithan Road, Chhatrapati

Sambhajingar, Maharashtra, India-431105.

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Corresponding Author*Vasave Nimba Bamnya**

Dr. Vedprakash Patil Pharmacy
College, Gevrai Tanda, Paithan Road,
Chhatrapati Sambhajingar,
Maharashtra, India-431105.

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ABSTRACT

Hypertension is a very common and serious condition that can lead to or complicate many health problems. Antihypertensive therapy has been used for almost 45 years to reduce the blood pressure and to prevent morbidity and mortality related to the hypertensive state. Cardiovascular events are related to the initial elevation of blood pressure; the benefits of treating malignant, severe or moderate hypertension are well established. Recently it has emphasized that the absolute risk of cardiovascular events is determined only in part by blood pressure, and that it is also influenced by age, gender, race and presence of cardiovascular risk factors. For example in older individuals where the absolute risk of vascular complication is greater than in younger individuals for any given level of blood pressure. Drug therapy has been shown to be extremely effective in reducing the incidence of stroke, congestive heart

failure and renal failure associated with elevated blood pressure. Experimental data suggesting differences in the ability of antihypertensive drugs to inhibit atherosclerosis in animals models are also of interest, but again the relation of the findings to the clinical situation is unknown. Thiazide diuretics, beta blockers, calcium antagonists, Angiotensin Converting Enzyme Inhibitors and Alpha blockers can produce regression of Left Ventricular Hypertrophy. While Left Ventricular Hypertrophy is a clearly a strong and independent predictor for coronary disease, it remains to be shown that a lower risk for coronary morbid events exists in patients whose Left Ventricular Hypertrophy has undergone regression over and above that attribute to blood pressure reduction.

KEYWORDS: Hypertension, antihypertensive drugs, eclampsia, Pre-eclampsia, types and stages of hypertension, ACE inhibitors, treatment options for hypertension.

INTRODUCTION

HYPERTENSION

Hypertension is defined as abnormally high blood pressure (more than 120/80 mm Hg) in the arteries. Persistent increase in systemic arterial blood pressure is known as hypertension. Usually a mean arterial pressure greater than 110 mm Hg under resting conditions is considered to be hypertensive; this level normally occurs when the diastolic blood pressure is greater than 90 mm Hg and the systolic pressure is greater than about 135-140 mm Hg. Hypertension is generally symptomless, but increases the risk of various other cardiovascular diseases like stroke, heart attack and non-cardiovascular diseases like renal damage, end stage of renal failure, etc. Although hypertension is a common health problem with some times devastating consequence, it often remains asymptomatic until late in its course. A sustained diastolic pressure greater than 90 mm Hg, or a sustained systolic pressure in excess of 140 mm Hg, is considered to constitute hypertension. 90-95% of hypertension is idiopathic (essential hypertension), which is compatible with long life, unless a myocardial infarction, cerebrovascular accident, or other complication supervenes. Most of the remainder of "benign hypertension" is secondary to renal disease or, less often to narrowing of the renal artery, usually by an atherosclerotic plaque (Renovascular hypertension). Infrequently, hypertension is secondary to diseases of the adrenal glands, such as primary aldosteronism, Cushing syndrome, pheochromocytoma, or other disorders. Various determinants play an important role in the development and in the causation of premature cardiovascular risk over and beyond hypertension.

Hypertension or high blood pressure is a very common and serious condition that can lead to or complicate many health problems. The risk of cardiovascular morbidity and mortality is directly correlated with blood pressure. Risks of stroke, MI, angina, heart failure, kidney failure or early death from a cardiovascular cause are directly correlated with BP. Hypertension is often called "the silent killer" because it generally has no symptoms until a serious complication develops. There are three general types of hypertension. Essential or primary hypertension occurs when the condition has no known cause. This form of hypertension cannot be cured, but it can be controlled. More than 90% of individuals with hypertension have essential hypertension. Genetic factors may play an important role in the

development of essential hypertension. When hypertension is caused by another condition or disease process, it is called secondary hypertension. Fewer than 10% of patients have secondary hypertension; where either a co-morbid disease or drug is responsible for elevating BP. In most of these cases renal dysfunction resulting from severe chronic kidney disease or renal vascular disease is the most common secondary cause.

Hypertension has a variety of causes. Blood pressure generally tends to rise with age. Hypertension can also be caused by other medical conditions, such as thyroid disease or chronic kidney disease. Hypertension may also be a side effect of certain medications, such as over-the-counter cold medications and oral contraceptives and other hormone drugs.

Types of Hypertension

Pressure Category	Systolic Pressure mm Hg	Diastolic Pressure mm Hg
Normal	90-119	60-79
Pre-hypertension	120-139	80-89
Stage 1	140-149	90-99
Stage 2	>160	>100
Isolated Systolic Hypertension	>140	<90

Hypertension is divided into two types

- A) Primary Hypertension (Essential hypertension)
- B) Secondary Hypertension (Non-Essential hypertension)

A) PRIMARY HYPERTENSION

It results when arterial blood pressure is increased due to increased peripheral resistance. It is further divided into two types namely: benign and malignant hypertension.

a) Benign hypertension

Here, there is a moderate increase in blood pressure with systolic pressure of 200 mm Hg and the diastolic pressure of above 100 mm Hg. However, in resting condition and sleep, the blood pressure returns to normal level. Later, if there is increase in blood pressure it will not come back to normal level in resting conditions.

b) Malignant hypertension

Here, the blood pressure elevated to a great extent of about 250 mm Hg of systolic pressure and 150 mm Hg of diastolic pressure. It produces severe symptoms like renal disease, retinal disease, and being a fatal disease, it causes death within few years. Some of the

characteristics of primary or essential hypertension are, 1) The mean arterial pressure is increased 40-60 % 2) The renal blood flow in the later stages is decreased about one half of normal. 3) The resistance to blood flow through the kidney is increased 2-4 fold. 4) The kidneys will not excrete adequate amounts of salt and water unless the arterial pressure is high.

B) SECONDARY HYPERTENSION

The different forms of secondary hypertension are

a) Cardiovascular hypertension

- a) Atherosclerosis- hardening and narrowing of blood vessels
- b) Coarctation of aorta- narrowing of aorta.

b) Renal hypertension

- a) Stenosis renal arteries- narrowing of one or both renal arteries, so that the renal function is impaired.
- b) Glomerulonephritis-nephritis with inflammation of the capillary loops in the renal glomeruli.

c) Endocrine hypertension

It occurs due to

- a) Pheochromocytoma- tumor in adrenal medulla.
- b) Hyperaldosteronism- excess secretion of aldosterone from adrenal cortex Conn's syndrome.
- c) Cushing's syndrome- excess secretion of cortisone and Gigantism or Acromegaly- excess secretion of growth hormone.

d) Neurogenic hypertension

Acute hypertension can be caused by strong stimulation of the sympathetic nervous system.

- a) Section of the baroreceptors nerves.
- b) Lesions in tractus solitarius.
- c) Increased intracranial pressure.

THE COMMON DETERMINANTS

- a) **Age and Sex:** BP generally rises with age in both male and female. The rise is more

sleep in the middle age and thereafter. At initial phase, pressure is more in men while in later phase rise is more in women.

b) Weight: the rise in BP with respect to weight is found to be directly proportional.

c) Alcohol consumption: it is also reported that alcohol intake than positively increase the BP, but the reason is not clear.

d) Geographic variation: geographical variation can affect BP via variable contributing factors like TPR, hypoxia, primitive condition, etc.

e) Smoking: tobacco combustion results in nicotine and carbon monoxide production, a potent vasoconstrictor leading to development of hypertension.

f) Salt consumption: Salt intake can promote rigidity to vascular smooth muscle and therefore excessive salt intake (more than 8 -10 gm. per day) may result in hypertension.

g) Genetic predisposition: Based upon survey it is now believed that hypertension may be the result of typical genetic makeup.

SYMPTOMS OF HYPERTENSION

The clinical features may be due to the elevated BP itself, target organ involvement or due to underlying diseases, as in secondary hypertension. Symptoms due to hypertension:

1. Head ache: This occurs usually in morning hours. It is throbbing and usually frontal.
2. Dizziness: The patients feel unsteadily.
3. Epistaxis: This occurs due to increased pressure, causing rupture of the capillaries of the nose. The bleeding reduces circulating volume, and lowers the BP

a) Symptoms due to affection of organs

1. CVS

- a) Dyspnea on exertion (insipient LVF)
- b) Anginal chest pain (IHD)
- c) Palpitation

2. Kidneys

- a) Hematuria
- b) Nocturia
- c) Polyuria

3. CNS

Transient is chemic attacks (TIA or stroke) with focal neurological deficit.

- a) Hypertensive encephalopathy (head ache, vomiting, convulsion, unconsciousness, focal neurological deficit).
- b) Dizziness, tinnitus and syncope.
- c) Retina: Blurred vision or sudden blindness.

b) Symptoms due to underlying diseases

1. Edema and puffy face- Acute nephritis.
2. Weight gain, hirsutism and stria- Cushing's syndrome.
3. Weight loss, tremors, palpitation and sweating.
4. Hyperthyroidism/ pheochromocytoma
5. Weakness- hyperaldosteronism.
6. Joint pain, bronchospasm and peripheral vascular disease.
7. Symptoms- polyarteritis nodosa.

CAUSES OF HYPERTENSION

1. Renal

- a) Acute nephritis
- b) Interstitial nephritis and pyelonephritis
- c) Polycystic kidneys
- d) Renal artery stenosis

2. Vascular: Arteriosclerosis, coarctation of aorta.

3. Endocrine: Pheochromocytoma, Cushing's syndrome, thyrotoxicosis, myxedema.

4. Neurological: Raised intracranial tension, lead encephalopathy, etc.

5. Miscellaneous: Polycythemia, aortic incompetence, toxemia of pregnancy, periarteris nodosa gout, etc.

6. High Cholesterol level

High blood pressure and high cholesterol level are also a linked in heart disease such as hypertension. When the arteries becomes hardened and narrowed with cholesterol plaque and calcium (atherosclerosis), heart has to strain much harder to pump blood through them. As a result, blood pressure becomes abnormally high.

Cholesterol Blocking Artery

Fig. Cholesterol blocking artery.

PATHOGENESIS OF HYPERTENSION

The multiple mechanism of hypertension constitutes aberrations of the normal physiologic regulation of blood pressure. Regulation of normal blood pressure: The blood pressure level is a complex trait that is determined by the interaction of multiple genetic, environmental, and demographic factors that influence to hemodynamic variables: cardiac output and total peripheral resistance. Total peripheral resistance is predominantly determined at the level of the arterioles and depends on the effect of neural and hormonal influence. Normal vascular tone reflects the balance between humoral vasoconstriction influences (including angiotensin II and catecholamine) and vasodilators (including kinins, prostaglandins, and nitric oxide). Resistance vessels also exhibit autoregulation, whereby increased blood flow induced vasoconstriction to protect against tissue hyper perfusion. Other local factors such as pH and hypoxia, as well as neural interactions (α - and β - adrenergic systems), may important.

The kidneys play an important role in blood pressure regulation, as follows

- 1) Through the renin-angiotensin system, the kidney influences both peripheral resistance and sodium homeostasis. Renin elaborated by the juxta glomerular cells of kidney transforms plasma angiotensinogen to angiotensin I, which is then converted to angiotensin II by angiotensin converting enzyme (ACE). Angiotensin II raises blood pressure by increasing both peripheral resistance (direct action on vascular SMCs) and blood volume (stimulation of aldosterone secretion, increase in distal tubular reabsorption of sodium).
- 2) The kidney also produced a variety of vasodepressor or antihypertensive substances

(including prostaglandins and nitric oxide) that presumably counterbalance the vasopressor effects of angiotensin.

- 3) When blood volume is reduced, the glomerular filtration rate falls, leading to increased reabsorption of sodium and water by proximal tubules and thereby conserving sodium and expanding blood volume.
- 4) Glomerular filtration rate- independent natriuretic factors including atrial natriuretic peptide, secreted by heart atria in response to volume expansion, inhibit sodium reabsorption in distal tubules and cause vasodilation.
- 5) When renal excretory function is impaired, increased atrial pressure is a compensatory mechanism that helps restore fluid and electrolyte balance.

EFFECT OF HYPERTENSION ON DIFFERENT SYSTEMS

The common organs damage by long standing hypertension are heart, blood vessels, retina and central nervous system.

CVS: Increased myocardial work leads to concentric hypertrophy of left ventricle, angina pectoris and accelerated coronary artery diseases. There is systolic as well as diastolic dysfunction.

Kidneys: Progressive arteriosclerosis involves both the efferent and afferent renal arteriols and capillaries of glomerular tuft. This leads to compromise in renal function, shrinkage of kidneys, proteinuria.

CNS: Hypertension may cause microaneurysms, which may rupture and cause cerebral hemorrhage. Accelerated atherosclerosis may cause cerebral thrombosis, embolism and infection. Cerebral arteriolar spasm may cause hypertensive encephalopathy.

BLOOD PRESSURE (BP)

Blood pressure (BP) is defined as lateral pressure exerted by the blood on the walls of the blood vessels while flowing through them. Blood pressure in a blood vessel depends upon two things.

- 1) Distance from the heart
- 2) Nature of the blood vessel.

Blood pressure is more in blood vessels close to the heart. Blood pressure is more in arterial

system than in the venous system. This is because walls of arteries are thicker and less elastic; the walls of the veins are thinner and more elastic. Normal blood pressure is 120/80 mmHg, Systolic BP (SBP) is the maximum BP during the ventricular systole- 120 mmHg. Range: 110-130 mmHg. Diastolic BP (DBP) is the minimum pressure during the ventricular diastole. It is 80 mmHg. Range: 70-90 mmHg.

Mean arterial blood pressure

It is not the arithmetic mean but it is less than that. It is because most of the time BP is closer to diastolic value than systolic value. It because duration of ventricular diastole is longer than duration of systole. Mean arterial BP=Diastolic BP+1/3 of pulse pressure i.e., $80+13=93$

Factor Effecting Blood Pressure

- 1) Volume of blood.
- 2) Force of contraction of the heart.
- 3) Heart rate and BP are inversely proportional.
- 4) Viscosity of blood.
- 5) Nature of the blood.
- 6) Elasticity of blood vessel.

Regulation of Blood Pressure

It means maintaining a constant blood pressure within a narrow variation. Both increase in blood pressure (hypertension) and decrease in blood pressure (hypotension) are harmful in the body. The mechanism of regulation of BP is divided in to two It groups.

- 1) Rapidly acting mechanism
- 2) Slow acting mechanism

Rapidly acting mechanism

This includes both nervous regulation as well as endocrine or hormonal regulation.

a) Nervous Regulation of BP

The smooth muscles of blood vessels will always remain in a state of contraction. Because of this the blood vessels remain in a state of constriction- vasoconstriction. The degree of vasoconstriction depends upon the sympathetic tone. When sympathetic tone increase the degree of vasoconstriction will also increase. When vasoconstriction increases total peripheral resistance (TPR) will increase which will in turn increase BP. It is known as vasomotor centre.

Baroreceptors and the sympathetic nervous system

Baroreflexes involving the sympathetic nervous system are responsible for the rapid moment to moment regulation of blood pressure. A fall in blood pressure causes pressure- sensitive neurons (baro-receptors in the aortic arch and carotid sinuses) to send fewer impulses to cardiovascular centers in the spinal cord. This prompts a reflex response of increased sympathetic and decreased parasympathetic output to the heart and vasculature, resulting in vasoconstriction and increased cardiac output. These changes result in a compensatory rise in blood pressure.

b) Endocrine or Hormonal regulation of BP

There are three important hormones taking part in regulation of BP.

- Renin- Angiotensin- Aldosterone mechanism or system.
- Regulation of BP by Vasopressin or ADH.
- Adrenalin (Epinephrine) and noradrenalin (nor epinephrine).

i) Renin- Angiotensin- Aldosterone mechanism or system

Suppose BP falls, it will stimulate the kidney. The juxta glomerular apparatus of the kidney will secrete renin. Renin acts as an enzyme. It acts on a plasma protein, angiotensin substrate and converts it into angiotensin I. The angiotensin I is converted into angiotensin II by the action of converting enzyme. Angiotensin II is a vasoconstrictor in action. It acts on the walls of blood vessels and increases the degree of vasoconstriction. TPR will increase; this will in turn increase the BP to normal. In addition to that angiotensin II stimulates adrenal cortex. This will increase the secretion of the hormone aldosterone. Aldosterone acts as kidneys. It increases the reabsorption of sodium and water. This will increase blood volume.

ii) Regulation of BP by Vasopressin or ADH

Suppose BP falls, that will stimulate hypothalamus. Hypothalamus in turn stimulates posterior pituitary. Posterior pituitary secretes vasopressin. It acts on the wall of blood vessels. It increases vasoconstriction. TPR increases and BP will increase to the normal level. In addition to this, ADH acts at the kidneys. It increases the reabsorption of water. That will increase blood volume, so BP increases to the normal level.

iii) Adrenaline (Epinephrine) and noradrenaline (nor epinephrine)

Suppose BP falls that will stimulate hypothalamus. Hypothalamus in turn stimulates sympathetic nervous system. This will in turn stimulate adrenal medulla. It secretes more adrenaline. Adrenaline acts at the wall of the blood vessels. It increases vasoconstriction. This will increase TPR, this will in turn increase BP to normal level.

Long Term Regulation of BP

Suppose the BP increases. This will increase G.F.R, this will increase urine output and water loss from the body. This will decrease blood volume, this will in turn decrease the BP.

REVIEW LITERATURE

1. Juan J. Bolivar (2013) et al: In this review author explained that causal link between an abnormal high salt intake and essential hypertension. A high salt intake 9-12g per day is a pleasant component of current normal diet, but it is abnormal from an evolutionary point of view. This review emphasized that hypertension is due to specific cause in a small fraction of cases, but in the vast majority of individuals 90%, its etiology cannot be determined. Such as Salt intake, abnormal regulation of the kidney function, origins of sympathetic nervous

system activation in essential hypertension, control of blood pressure by the kidneys. The relative stability of arterial blood pressure leads to the conclusion that it is a highly controlled variable.

2. Martin Thomas et al: Review suggests that hypertension is common diseases in the world and is an important risk factor of coronary events .The author explained that a precise definition of hypertension is difficult to establish because blood pressure is a continuous variable and has a skewed normal distribution within the population. In the epidemiology the prevalence of hypertension is increases with age. The Ethnic group Black people have a higher prevalence and incidence of hypertension than white people. Women are less likely than to develop hypertension at an early age. In the pathogenesis essential hypertension is multifactorial, complex and not clearly defined. Routine investigation includes serum urea, creatinine and electrolyte levels, blood glucose levels, echocardiogram chest X-ray.

3. Nazeer Ahmed, Ashley Martinelli, Catherine Kiruthi (2015) et al: Author explained the antihypertensive drugs classification by its site of action, target organ. By the giving example of cases all the classes of antihypertensive drugs are explained. Individually each class of drugs are suggests different action but each class is leads to reduced the hypertension not fully but reduce the signs of hypertension.

4. Sanjeev Gulati (2006) et al: In this review author tells that hypertension cause in children designated childhood hypertensioin. Prevalence of primary and secondary hypertension in children are reported to be 1-3%. Hypertension techniques and case definitions are discussed that automated oscillometric devices are useful. The common cause of hypertension in different age groups are discussed as newborn, infancy, 6-10 years, and adolescence. Clinical presentation young infants may present in acute distress with signs and symptoms of congestive heart failure . Evaluation of initial and additional is taken. Management of pediatric hypertension is divided by pharmacological and non pharmacological. Hypertensive emergencies are described with dose initial and maximum dose.

5. Mhamad Al-Hashimi and Jonathan P Thompson et al: Study of this review are explained the antihypertensive drugs that are commonly used in anesthesia and intensive care medicines .In this article guidelines for treatment of hypertension by National Institute for Health and Clinical Excellence, there is a 7% increase risk of mortality from ischemic heart

disease and a 10% increased risk from stroke with each 2 mmHg rise in blood pressure. Fluctuations in heart rate and arterial pressure during anesthesia and surgery are exaggerated in patients with hypertension.

6. Wilbert S Aronow (2012) et al: Review article suggests that the lifestyle measures are modification should be used to prevent mild hypertension and to decrease the dose levels of drugs needed to control hypertension. Weight reduction, consuming a diet rich in fruits vegetables, and low fat dairy products with a reduced amount of saturated fat and total fat, sodium reduction to not exceed to 1.5 grams daily, smoking cessation, regular aerobic physical activity. Use of antihypertensive drugs for therapy a meta-analysis of 147 randomized trials including 464,000 patients with hypertension showed that except for the extra protective effect of beta blockers given after myocardial infarction and a minor additional effect of calcium channel blockers in preventing stroke, use of beta blockers, Angiotensin Converting Enzyme Inhibitors , angiotensin receptor blockers , diuretics, and calcium channel blockers cause a similar reduction in coronary events and stroke for a given decrease in blood pressure.

7. Siyad A R (2011) et al: In this article reviewed that hypertension, or high blood pressure, is a very common and serious condition that can lead to or complicate many health problems. The risk of cardiovascular morbidity and mortality is directly correlated with BP. Risks of stroke, MI, angina, heart failure, kidney failure or early death from a cardiovascular cause are directly correlated with BP. The roles of drug treatment, diet control, exercise, etc. are discussed in this review.

8. Tadesse Melaku Abegaz, Yonas Getaye et al: In this article the hypertension is deemed the major cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide. It affects approximately 1 billion individuals globally HTN ranked as the leading single factor for Global Burden of Diseases, most notably in sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia. Globally, about 62% of cerebrovascular diseases and 49% of ischemic heart disease are attribute to elevated blood pressure. In developing countries, its morbidity and mortality are increasing due to a change in life style.

9. D Wong, P.N.W. Tsai et al: Article describes new antihypertensive agents currently available or under development that could impact perioperative management. It has been reported that each 5 mmHg reduction in diastolic can result in significant reduction in cardiovascular morbidity and mortality. Current evidence suggests that hypertension itself

should not be treated alone but include assessment of all cardiovascular risk factors. Newly developed antihypertensive drugs such as direct renin inhibitors are discussed.

10. KD Tripathi Essential of Medical Pharmacology et al: Author describes the recently developed available antihypertensive agents with each class of category to treat the hypertension in adults. There are many antihypertensive analogues developed that fewer are very effective in action by target the organ that cause the decrease in the risk in the hypertension. All beta blockers and calcium channel blockers are very efficient in the action. Aliskiren is one alone drugs developed that have direct renin inhibitor activity has been described.

OBJECTIVES

- To Discuss the causes of hypertension and how to reduce the risk of stroke, myocardial infarction.
- To Aware of cardiovascular risks and prevention of them to the people
- To Counsel to the patient for improve the maintenance of food consumption/intake that contains cholesterol.
- To Study the pharmacological basis and Non pharmacological basis treatment of hypertension and their importance
- To control hypertension and prevent the occurrence of cardiovascular diseases due to sustained high blood pressure, thereby reducing mortality and morbidity results improve the quality of life.
- To Management of hypertension by lifestyle modification includes restriction of salt intake, alcohol intake, weight control and exercise promotion of fruit and vegetable consumption.

HISTORY OF ANTIHYPERTENSIVE DRUGS

Antihypertensive are a class of drugs that are used to treat hypertension. Antihypertensive therapy seeks to prevent the complications of high blood pressure, such as stroke and myocardial infarction. Evidence suggests that reduction of the blood pressure by 5 mmHg can decrease the risk of stroke by 34%, of ischemic heart disease by 21%, reduce the likelihood of dementia, heart failure, and mortality from cardiovascular disease. There are many classes of antihypertensive which lower by different means. Among the most important most widely used are thiazide diuretics, calcium channel blockers, ACE inhibitors, angiotensin II receptor

antagonists, and beta blockers.

Which type of medications to use initially for hypertension has been subject of large studies and resulting national guidelines. The fundamental goal of treatment should be prevention of the important endpoints of hypertension, such as heart attack, stroke, and heart failure. Patient age, associated clinical conditions and end organ damage also play an important role in determining dosage and type of medication administered. The several classes of antihypertensive differ in side effects profile, ability to prevent endpoints, and cost. The choice of more expensive agents, where cheaper ones would be equally effective, may have negative impacts on national health care budgets. As of 2018, the best available evidence favors low dose thiazide diuretics as the first line treatment of choice for high blood pressure when drugs are necessary. Although clinical shows calcium channel blockers and thiazide type diuretics are preferred first line treatment for most people from both efficacy and cost point of view. An ACE inhibitors is recommended by NICE in the UK for those under 55 years old.

In the beginnings of 1960s, Helmut Stable, while working on decongestive drugs i.e. tolazoline and pentanolamine observed that increase in decongestive activity. The sympatholytic such as clonidine is developed by Mrs. Schwandf. At present renin antagonists do not have therapeutic potential while aldosterone antagonists may principally be used as diuretic agents saralasin is an example of angiotensin II competitive antagonist while captopril is introduced in (1977) is an example of orally effective converting enzyme inhibitor. Chlorthiazide diuretic was introduced in 1957.

Propranolol Beta blockers was discovered in 1964. Clonidine Alpha 2 agonist was discovered in 1966.

MANAGEMENT

Management of Hypertension is divided into two major types

- A) Pharmacological management of Hypertension
- B) Non-Pharmacological management of Hypertension

A. PHARMACOLOGICAL MANAGEMENT OF HYPERTENSION

Antihypertensive Drugs Definition of Antihypertensive

Antihypertensive are a class of drugs that are used to treat hypertension (high blood pressure).

Antihypertensive therapy seeks to prevent the complication of high blood pressure, such as stroke and myocardial infarction. Evidence suggests that reduction of blood pressure by 5 mmHg can decrease the stroke by 34% of ischemic heart disease by 21%, and reduce the likelihood of dementia, heart failure, and mortality from cardiovascular diseases.

Classification of Antihypertensive drugs

Antihypertensive drugs are classified under the following types

1. Angiotensin Converting Enzyme (ACE) Inhibitors
2. Angiotensin (AT₁ Receptor) Antagonists
3. Calcium Channel Blockers
4. Diuretics
5. Alpha Adrenergic Blockers
6. Beta Adrenergic Blockers
7. Alpha + Beta Adrenergic Blockers
8. Central Sympatholytic
9. Vasodilators

Chart of Antihypertensive Drugs with Example and Dose

Sr. No.	Class	Example	Dose
1	ACE Inhibitors	Captopril,	12.5-50 mg
		Enalapril	5-40 mg
		Lisinopril	2.5-10 mg
		Perindopril	4-8 mg
		Ramipril	1.25-10 mg
		Benazepril	2.5-10 mg
		Trandolapril	2-4 mg
		Fosinopril	10-40 mg
		Imidapril	5-20 mg
2	Angiotensin antagonists	Losartan	25-100 mg
		Valsartan	80-320 mg
		Telmisartan	40-80 mg
		Candesartan	8-32 mg
		Irbesartan	75-300 mg
		Olmesartan medoxomil	10-40 mg
3	Calcium Channel Blockers	Verapamil	120-480 mg
		Diltiazem	36-60 mg
		Nifedipine	10-90 mg
		Felodipine	2.5-20 mg
		Amlodipine	2.5-10 mg
		S(-)Amlidipine	2.5-5 mg
		Nitrendipine	5.20 mg

		Lacidipine	2-6 mg
		Benidine	4-8 mg
4	Diuretics	Thiazide Hydrochlorthiazide	12.5-50 mg
		Chlorthalidone	25-100 mg
		Loop Diuretics Furosemide	40-80 mg
		K ⁺ Sparing Spironolactone	50-400 mg
		Amiloride	5-10 mg
5	Beta Adrenergic Blockers	Propranolol	40-640 mg
		Metoprolol	50-400 mg
6	Alpha+Beta Adrenergic Blockers	Labetalol	50-400 mg
		Carvedilol	12.5-50 mg
7	Alpha Adrenergic Blockers	Prazosin	0.5-20 mg
		Terazosin	1-20 mg
8	Central sympatholytics	Clonidine	0.1-2.5 mg
		Methyldopa	250 mg
9	Vasodilators	Arteriolar Hydralazine	25-50 mg
		Minoxidil	10-25 mg
		Diazoxide	10-25 mg
		Arteriolar+ Venous Na Nitropruside	50mg

ANTIHYPERTENSIVE DRUGS

1. Diuretics Type Mechanism of Action

- Initial effects: through reduction of plasma volume and cardiac output.
- Long term effect: through decrease in total peripheral vascular resistance.

Side Effects

- Metabolic effects (uncommon with small doses): hypokalemia, hypomagnesaemia, hyponatremia, hyperuricemia, dyslipidemia(increased total and LDL cholesterol), impaired glucose tolerance, and hypercalcemia (with thiazides).
- Postural hypotension.
- Impotence in up to 22% of patients.

2. Beta - Adrenergic Blocking Agents Mechanisms of Action

- Initial decrease in cardiac output, followed by reduction in peripheral ascular resistance.
- Other actions include decrease plasma renin activity, resetting of baroreceptors, release of vasodilator prostaglandins, and blockade of pre- Junctional beta- receptors.

Side Effects

- Bronchospasm and obstructive airway disease.
- Bradycardia
- Metabolic effects (raise triglycerides levels and decrease HDL cholesterol; may worsen insulin sensitivity and cause glucose intolerance). Increased incidence of diabetes mellitus.
- Coldness of extremities
- Fatigue
- Mask symptoms of hypoglycemia

3. Calcium channel blockers

- Dihydropyridine: nifedipine, amlodipine, felodipine, nicardipine, lacidipine.
- Non dihydropyridine.
- Phenylalkylamine: verapamil.
- Benzothiazepine: diltiazem.

Mechanisms of action

- Decrease in the concentration of free intracellular calcium ions results in decreased contraction and vasodilation.
- Diuretic effect through increase in renal blood flow and glomerular filtration rate.
- Inhibition of aldosterone secretion.

Side Effects

- Dihydropyridine: flushing, headache, and lower limb edema.
- Non dihydropyridine: aggravation of heart failure and heart block. Verapamil may cause constipation.

4. Angiotensin Converting Enzyme Inhibitors

- Class I: captopril
- Class II (prodrug) : e.g., ramipril, enalapril, perindopril
- Class III (water soluble) : lisinopril.

Mechanism of Action

- Inhibition of circulating and tissue angiotensin- converting enzyme.

- Increased formation of bradykinin and vasodilatory prostaglandins.
- Decreased secretion of aldosterone; help sodium excretion.

Side Effects

- Cough (10 - 30%): a dry irritant cough with tickling sensation in the throat.
- Skin rash (6%).
- Postural hypotension in salt depleted or blood volume depleted patients.
- Angioedema (0.2%) : life threatening.
- Renal failure: rare, high risk with bilateral renal artery stenosis.
- Hyperkalaemia
- Teratogenicity

5. Angiotensin Receptor Blockers Mechanism of Action

They act by blocking type I angiotensin II receptors generally, producing more blockade of the renin - angiotensin - aldosterone axis.

6. Sympatholytics And Alpha Adrenergic Blockers Types

- Alpha 1-receptor blockers: prazosin, doxazosin.
- Centrally acting alpha 2- agonists: methyldopa, clonidine.
- Peripherally acting adrenergic antagonists: reserpine.
- Imidazoline receptor agonists: rilmenidine, moxonidine.

Side Effects

- Prazosin: postural hypotension, diarrhea, occasional tachycardia, and tolerance (due to fluid retention).
- Methyldopa: sedation, hepatotoxicity, hemolytic anemia, and tolerance.
- Reserpine: depression, lethargy, weight loss, peptic ulcer, diarrhea, and impotence.
- Clonidine: dry mouth, sedation, bradycardia, impotence, and rebound hypertension if stopped suddenly.

7. Direct Arterial Vasodilators

Types: hydralazine, diazoxide, nitroprusside, and minoxidil (see chapter 10).

Mechanisms of Actions

- It acts by direct arterial vasodilation leads to reduce the blood pressure

- It relax the smooth muscles in blood vessels causes the vessels to dilate

Side Effects

- Chest pain
- Heart palpitations
- Rapid heart beat

Commonly Used Oral Antihypertensive Medications

Sr. No.	Class	Generic Name	Daily Dose (mg)	Common Brands	Maximum Dose
1	Diuretics	Indapamide	1.25-5	Natrilix	2.5
				Natrilix SR	1.5
		Chlorthalidone	25-50	Hygrotone	50
		Frusemide	20-400	Lasix	40
		Bumetanide	1-4 (or more)	Burinex	1
2	Betaadrenergic blockers	Atenolol	25-100	Tenormin	50-100
				Blockium	50-100
				Blockium Diu *	50
		Metoprolol	50-200	Betaloc	100
Bisoprolol	2.5-10	Concor	5-10		
		Concor 5 Plus*	5		
3	Calcium antagonists	Verapamil	120-480	Isoptin retard	240
				Tarka***	120
		Diltiazem	90-240	Tildium	60
				Altiazem	60
		Nifedipine	20-80	Adalat retard	20
				Epilat retard	20
Amlodipine	2.5-10	Norvasc	5-10		
		Amilo	5		
4	ACE inhibitors	Captopril	50-150	Capoten	25-50
				Capozide	50
				Captopril	25-50
		Enalapril	2.5-40	Renetec	10-20
				Co-renetec	10-20
				Ezapril	10-20
		Lisinopril	10-40	Zestril	5-10-20
Zestoretic	20				
Ramipril	2.5-20	Tritace	1.25-2.5		
Perindopril	2-8	Coversyl	2-4		
5	Angiotensin Receptor Blockers	Losartan	25-100	Cozaar	50
				Losartan	50
		Valsartan	80-320	Tareg	80-160
				Co-Tareg	80-160
		Co-Diovan	160		
Telmisartan	20-80	Micardis	40-80		
	Alpha-adrenergic	Prazocin	1-16	Minipress	1-2

6	blockers	Doxazocin	1-16	Cardura	1-4
		Methyldopa	500-2000	Aldomet	250-500
7	Centrally acting drugs	Clonidine	0.1-1.2	Catapres	0.1-0.3
		Rilmenidine	1-2	Rilmenidine	1
		Reserpine	0.1	Brenardine	0.1

B. NON-PHARMACOLOGICAL MANAGEMENT OF HYPERTENSION

In the initial phase of hypertension (high, normal or mild hypertension), the non-pharmacological measures can lower the B.P. in most of individuals. In some patients, who do not show any reduction even after 04-06 months need drug therapy. It is harmless treatment and helpful either to eliminate the requirement of drug or reduce the dose as well as dose regiment. Non pharmacological approaches to the reduction of blood pressure generally are advisable as the initial approach to treatment of patients with diastolic blood pressure in the range of 90 to 95 mmHg. Further, these approaches will augment the effectiveness of pharmacological therapy in patients with higher level blood pressure. Non pharmacological methods to lower blood pressure allow the patient to participate actively in the management of his or her disease. Reduction of weight, restriction of salt, and moderation in the use of alcohol may be reduced blood pressure and improve the effect of drug treatment. In addition, regular isotonic exercise also lowers blood pressure in hypertensive patients.

Smoking per se does not cause hypertension. However, smokers do have a higher incidence of malignant hypertension, and smoking is major risk factor for coronary heart disease. Hypertensive patients have an exceptionally great incentive to stop smoking. Consumption of caffeine can raise blood pressure and elevate plasma concentrations of nor epinephrine, but long term consumption of caffeine causes tolerance to these effects and has not been associated with the development of hypertension.

a) Reduction of Body Weight

Obesity and hypertension are closely associated, and the degree of obesity is positively correlated with the incidence of hypertension. Obese hypertensives may lower their blood pressure by losing weight regardless of a change in salt consumption. The mechanism by which obesity causes hypertension is unclear, but increases the secretion of insulin in obesity could result in insulin mediated enhancement of renal tubular reabsorption of Na⁺ and an expansion of extracellular volume. Obesity is also associated with increased activity of the sympathetic nervous system. A combination of aerobic physical exercise and dietary counseling may enhance compliance.

b) Sodium Restriction

Severe restriction of salt will lower the blood pressure in most hospitalised hypertensive patients; this treatment method was advocated prior to the development of effective antihypertensive drugs. However severe salt restriction is not practical from a standpoint of compliance. Several studies have shown that moderate restriction of salt intake to approximately per day (2 g Na⁺) will, on average, lower blood pressure by 12 mm Hg systolic and 5 mm Hg diastolic. An additional benefit of salt restriction is improved responsiveness to some antihypertensive drugs.

c) Alcohol Restriction

Consumption of alcohol can raise blood pressure, but it is unclear how much alcohol must be consumed to observe this effect. Heavy consumption of alcohol increases the risk of cerebrovascular accidents but not coronary heart disease. In the fact, small amount of ethanol have been found to protect against the development of coronary artery disease. The mechanism by which alcohol raises blood pressure is unknown, but it may involve increased transport of Ca²⁺ into vascular smooth muscle cells. Excessive intake of alcohol also may result in poor compliance with antihypertensive regimens. All hypertensive patients should be advised to restrict consumption of ethanol to more than 30 ml per day.

d) Physical Exercise

Increased physical activity lowers rates of cardiovascular disease in men. It is not known if this beneficial effect is secondary to an antihypertensive response to exercise. Lack of physical activity is associated with a higher incidence of hypertension. Regular isotonic exercise reduces blood volume and plasma catecholamines and elevates plasma concentration of atrial natriuretic factor. The beneficial effect of exercise can occur in subjects who demonstrate no change in body weight or salt intake during the training period.

e) Relaxation and Biofeedback therapy

The fact that long term stressful stimuli can cause sustained hypertension in animals has given credence to the possibility that relaxation therapy will lower blood pressure in some hypertensive patients. Only those few patients with mild hypertension who wish to use this method should be encouraged to try, and these patients should be closely followed and receive pharmacological treatment if necessary.

DIET FOR A HYPERTENSIVE PATIENT ECLAMPSIA

Hypertension in pregnant women is known as pre-eclampsia. Pre-eclampsia can progress to a life-threatening condition called eclampsia, which is the development of protein in the urine, generalized swelling, and severe seizures. Other symptoms indicating that brain function is becoming impaired may precede these seizures such as nausea, vomiting, headaches, and vision loss. It may be of two types: a) A hypertensive woman becomes pregnant. b) Pregnancy induced hypertension. In both cases, drugs which are safe in pregnancy must be used.

The development of hypertension, accompanied by proteinuria and edema in the third trimester of pregnancy, is referred to as preeclampsia. This syndrome occurs in 5% to 10% of pregnancies, particularly with first pregnancies in women older than age 35 year. In those severely affected, convulsive seizure may appear which are then termed as eclampsia. By long historical precedent, preeclampsia and eclampsia have been referred to as toxemia of pregnancy. No bloodborn toxin has ever been identified, however, and so the historically sanctified term (still in use) is clearly misnomer. Full blown eclampsia may lead to disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC), with all of its attendant widespread ischemic organ injuries, and so eclampsia is potentially fatal. Placental hypoperfusion with an increased predisposition to the development of infarction. Clinically, preeclampsia appears insidiously in the 24th to 25th weeks of gestation, with the development of edema, proteinuria, and rising blood pressure. Should the condition evolve into eclampsia, renal function is impaired, the blood pressure mounts, and convulsions may appear. Prompt therapy early in the course aborts the organ changes, with clearance of all abnormalities.

COUNSELING

Recommendations

- Maintain a healthy weight
- Exercise regularly
- Follow a healthy eating plan and limit the amount of salt in your food.
- Avoid smoking. If you already smoke, try to stop
- If you drink alcohol, try to limit the amount the you drink
- Avoid bush medicines as these could affect the treatment you are taking.
- Read food labels to see how much sodium or salts is in the food.

In addition you need to

Check your blood pressure regularly, Take the medications that your doctor prescribes regularly Take time to relax and learn, how to manage stress.

Eating Habits Avoid

Salted potato or corn chips, Reduction in saturated fat, Salted peanuts, Fried chicken or other fried foods, Canned foods such as luncheon meats, chopped ham, Vienna sausages and corned beef, High salt seasonings such as garlic salt, onion salt, season-all etc., Preparing foods with lots of oil, Salt or corned fish, Pigtail, salt beef, salted pig snout, Salami, bolgna sausage, ham or other salted meats, Soft drinks, Adding salt to your food at the table.

You should eat

Five servings of fresh fruits and vegetables every day.

Also try to have regular servings of

Whole wheat bread, whole grain cereals such as brown rice, Pasta, potatoes, Increase in take of fiber, Beans, nuts Low fat cheeses, low fat milk, Lean meats, fish, chicken without the skin.

DIAGNOSIS**a) General Examination**

1. Moon face, buffalo hump and truncal obesity- Cushing's syndrome.
2. Puffy face, rough skin, obesity- Myxedema.
3. Tremors, tachycardia, exophthalmos and goitre- Hyperthyroidism.
4. Prognathism, clubbed hand, coarse features- Acromegaly.
5. Pigmentation- neurofibromatosis.
6. Radiofemoral delay and collateral vessels over the chest wall- Coarction of aorta
7. Weaker left radial- Preductal coarctation.
8. Waterhammer pulse- Aortic incompetence

b) Cardiovascular System

1. Cardiomegaly.
2. Third and fourth heart sound gallop.
3. Loud second heart sound.
4. Early diastolic murmur- due to AI.

c) Respiratory System

1. Basal crepitations- LVF. 2.
2. Rhonchi- LVF, polyarteritis nodosa.

d) Abdomen

1. Hepatomegaly- cardiac failure.
2. Palpable kidney lump- Polycystic kidney, hypernephroma
3. Bruit over renal artery- Renal artery stenosis.
4. Bruit over abdominal aorta- Abdominal aortic aneurysm.

TREATMENT**Lifestyle measures**

Lifestyle modification should be used to prevent mild hypertension and to decrease the dose levels of drugs needed to control hypertension. Weight reduction, consuming a diet rich in fruits, vegetables, and low-fat dairy products with a reduced amount of saturated fat and total fat, sodium reduction to not exceed 1.5 grams daily, smoking cessation, regular aerobic physical activity, avoidance of excessive alcohol intake, avoidance of excessive caffeine, and avoidance of drugs which can increase blood pressure including nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, glucocorticoids, and sympathomimetic are recommended. Implementing a national salt reduction program is likely a simple and cost effective way of improving public health.

Examination

A full examination is required in addition to measurement of blood pressure. Height and weight should be measured and body mass index (BMI) throughout, signs of secondary causes of hypertension should be looked for. Cardiovascular examination should concentrate on heart rhythm, evidence of heart failure, LVH and arterial disease. Abdominal examination should look for renal masses and bruits (an unusual sound that blood makes when it rushes past an obstruction in an artery). Neurological examination should include assessment of memory, evidence of neurological deficit and the appearance of both retinas, to look for hypertensive retinopathy. Hypertensive retinopathy is another example of end organ damage. Features include the appearance of "cotton wool" spots, flame shaped hemorrhages, muscular edema, exudates and eventually papilledema. The severity of retinopathy is divided into four grades with Grade IV being the most severe and associated with malignant hypertension.

Investigation

Following are the routine and additional investigations carried out in patients with essential hypertension:

Routine investigation

- Serum urea, creatinine and electrolyte levels
- Blood glucose levels
- Lipid profile

Urine analysis for proteinuria and hematuria

- Echocardiogram

Additional investigation

- X-Ray
- Echocardiogram

Unless a secondary cause of hypertension is suspected, routine investigation are carried out in essential hypertension as listed above. This are used to assess the overall level of cardiovascular risk and to look for any evidence of end organ damage.

Urine analysis is important because proteinuria is a sensitive marker of early hypertensive renal damage and may be associated with an increase in plasma urea and creatinine levels. Established micro albuminuria is a predictor of progression of renal disease in hypertensive patient and early recognition and commencement of ACE inhibitor therapy has been shown to slow the progression of worsening renal renal function.

An electrocardiogram is used to screen for LVH and may show evidence of underlying ischemia, previous myocardial infarction and the presence of arrhythmias. Echocardiography is indicated if there is suspicion of LVH or any other evidence of end organ damage.

Chest X-ray is not routinely indicated in the hypertensive patient unless there is evidence of underlying respiratory disease, heart failure or the suspicion of a secondary cause, such as coarctation of the aorta.

CHILDHOOD HYPERTENSION

INTRODUCTION

Hypertension is one of the commonest diseases with an estimated worldwide prevalence of 1

billion. Data from the 3rd National Health and Nutritional Assessment Survey reveals that in US, one-third of people were unaware of this problem and another one third had blood pressure control below established goals. To add to this is the observation in the 7th Joint National Committee on Prevention, Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Pressure report that each increment of 20 mm Hg in systolic or 10 mm Hg diastolic pressure doubles the risk of cardiovascular disease. There are no similar data in children. Where the age, gender and height need to be taken into account while interpreting blood pressure values. Essential hypertension has been found to be associated with family history of hypertension, IUGR, oligonephronia, obesity and elevated uric acid levels. According to studies in adult populations, the effective treatment of hypertension reduces the risk of coronary heart disease, stroke, renal disease, and congestive heart failure.

1. Prevalence of Primary and Secondary Hypertension

The prevalence of hypertension in children is reported to be 1-3%. In recent years, the prevalence of hypertension in school-aged children appears to be increasing, perhaps as a result of the increased prevalence of obesity. School-based blood pressure screening and measurement of height and weight in 5102 children, revealed a prevalence of 4.5%, which is higher than that reported earlier. The majority of these children have mild hypertension, most often primary (essential). A small group of children have much higher blood pressures usually due to a secondary cause. The prevalence of persistent secondary hypertension in children is 0.1% and renal disease predominates in this group. Education, anticipatory guidance, early detection, accurate diagnosis and effective therapy may help improve the long term outcomes of children and adolescents with hypertension.

2. Hypertension—Techniques and Case Definitions

All measurements used in constructing the task force tables were made with a standard mercury sphygmomanometer. Despite the availability of electronic monitors, the mercury instrument remains the method of choice. The aneroid sphygmomanometer requires periodic calibration. Automated oscillometric devices are useful but expensive and require maintenance and calibration. However, these automated devices can be very helpful in evaluating infants and small children in whom resting, quiet, auscultator readings are difficult to obtain. The cuff should encircle at least 80-100% of the arm and the bladder length should be >40% of the arm circumference. Inappropriately small cuffs give aberrantly high readings; inappropriately large cuffs will underestimate the true reading. Measurements should be

taken after 3 to 5 minutes of resting. Children should have measurements taken while sitting, with the arm at the level of the heart, and infants should have measurements taken while supine. Ambulatory blood pressure monitoring (ABPM) is based on the principle that repeated measurements of blood pressure through 24-hr provide an approximation of true blood pressure than does a single measurement. Because ABPM values have not been precisely correlated with single or repeated conventional cuff measurements, cuff and ABPM measurements cannot be used interchangeably, either for clinical management or in trials of antihypertensive agents; both types of measurements therefore should be evaluated according to respective standard tables.

A definition of hypertension ideally is based on a threshold level of blood pressure that divides those at risk for adverse outcomes from those who have no increased risk. The normative values are based on the "The Fourth Report on the Diagnosis, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Pressure in Children and Adolescents", as follows

- Hypertension is defined as average systolic and/or diastolic pressure >95th percentile for gender, age and height on >3 occasions.
- Prehypertension is defined as average systolic or diastolic pressures between 90.95th percentiles.

These children should be observed carefully and evaluated if risk. Factors like obesity are present; tracking data suggest that this subgroup is more likely to develop overt hypertension over time than normotensive children. • Adolescents with blood pressure levels more than 120/80 mm Hg should be considered prehypertensive. • A patient with blood pressure levels >95th percentile in a physician's office or clinic, who is normotensive outside a clinical setting, has white-coat hypertension. • If the blood pressure is >95th percentile, it should be staged. If stage 1 (95th percentile to the 99th percentile plus 5 mm Hg), measurements should be repeated on 2 more occasions. If hypertension is confirmed, evaluation should proceed. If blood pressure is stage 2 (>99th percentile plus 5 mm Hg), prompt referral should be made for evaluation and therapy. If the patient is symptomatic, immediate referral and treatment are indicated. All children should have yearly blood pressure evaluation beyond 3 years of age. There is an increased risk of hypertension in children with history of hypertension in family members, those who are obese, IUGR or have urinary infections and renal scars.

3. White Coat Hypertension

These children have isolated office hypertension in that their blood pressure is normal when

measured at home, at work, or by ABPM. These patients have a relatively benign outcome compared to those with sustained hypertension. They may be at increased risk for eventual sustained hypertension and cardiovascular disease, although the risk of cardiovascular complications appears low as long as the ambulatory pressure remains normal.

4. Causes

Hypertension is usually described as primary (essential) or secondary due to a definable cause. The younger the patient and more severe the hypertension, the more likely that a secondary cause will be found. Most acute hypertension in childhood is due to glomerulonephritis. Chronic hypertension is commonly associated with renal parenchymal disease and only a small proportion have renovascular hypertension, pheochromocytoma or coarctation of the aorta. Late in the first decade and into the second decade of life, primary hypertension begins to predominate. Coarctation of the aorta accounts for one third cases of hypertension in neonatal period and infancy. Reno vascular causes are amongst the curable forms of hypertension. In Asia, aortoarteritis is common and accounts for most patients with malignant hypertension.

5. Comorbid Factors

Children with blood pressure who are in higher percentiles tend to track in those percentiles in adulthood. Obesity is a common cofactor in the development of essential hypertension. Obesity contributes to blood pressure control through high sodium intake and insulin resistance. The “syndrome X” of hypertension, obesity, hyperlipidemia and diabetes mellitus is a major cause of long-term cardiovascular morbidity and mortality.

Sleep disorders including sleep apnea are associated with hypertension; approximately 15% of children snore, and 1-3% have sleep disordered breathing. Repetitive loud snoring followed by silent periods of apnea usually represents the syndrome of obstructive sleep apnea. Because of the associations of hypertension with sleep disorders, particularly among overweight children, a history of sleeping patterns should be obtained. Clinical Presentation Young infants may present in acute distress with signs and symptoms of congestive heart failure. In contrast, after infancy hypertension is usually silent. Patients with severe hypertension may have headache, vision changes, nosebleeds, or nausea and should be treated immediately. Presence of edema, oliguria, and hematuria suggests rapidly progressive renal failure. Presence of joint pains, rash and systemic symptoms suggests connective tissue disorders. Hypertensive emergencies are defined as the presence of severe hypertension

associated with life threatening or organ-threatening complications, including encephalopathy (seizures, stroke, and focal deficits), acute heart failure, and pulmonary edema, dissecting aortic aneurysm or acute renal failure.

Attention should to be paid on physical examination to anthropometric measurements, height, and weight and body mass index. It may also show features of the specific cause, e.g. weak pulses or blood pressure difference between the upper and lower limbs in coarctation of the aorta, café-au-lait patches or features of neurofibromatosis with renal artery disease and abdominal masses in polycystic kidney disease. Signs and symptoms of cardiomegaly, hypertensive retinopathy or neurological involvement are important, since they indicate longstanding hypertension.

Common Causes of Hypertension in Different Age Groups.

Age group	Common Causes
Newborns	Renal artery thrombosis, renal artery stenosis, congenital malformation, coarctation of aorta, bronchopulmonary dysplasia
Infancy-6 yr.	Renal parenchymal disease, coarctation of aorta, renal artery stenosis
6-10 Year	Essential hypertension, renal artery stenosis
Adolescence	Essential hypertension, renal parenchymal disease

6. Management of Pediatric Hypertension

The goal of treatment is to decrease the short- and long-term risks of cardiovascular diseases and end-organ disease. Reducing the blood pressure alone is insufficient for this objective; the issues of obesity, hyperlipidemia, smoking and glucose intolerance must also be addressed. Most nephrologists agree that therapy is warranted in children who have persistent elevation of blood pressure above the 99th percentile. In young adults who were being followed up in the Bogalusa Heart Study but who died from accidental injuries, an autopsy series revealed significant and independent correlations between childhood hypertension and hypercholesterolemia and the early development of aortic and coronary atherosclerosis. Studies in adult patients have shown that the treatment of mild to moderate hypertension decreases the risk of stroke and coronary heart disease.

Life style modifications

Currently the initial treatment for hypertension involves weight reduction, exercise and dietary intervention. Weight reduction in children, as in adults, is a goal that is extremely

difficult to achieve. Exercise is helpful in reducing weight and both systolic and diastolic blood pressure levels. It must be undertaken on a continuing basis to have lasting benefit in the treatment of hypertension. Combinations of aerobic and static exercise should be followed. Dietary salt restriction has a very important place in the control of blood pressure. The current recommendation for adequate daily sodium intake is only 1.2 g/day for 4- to 8-year-olds and 1.5 g/day for older children.

Pharmacological management

Although conservative measures clearly can reduce blood pressure, these options are often insufficient for the treatment of hypertension because of patient and family compliance problems. The indications for antihypertensive therapy are

(i) Symptomatic hypertension, (ii) secondary hypertension, (iii) hypertensive target-organ damage, (iv) diabetes and (v) persistent hypertension despite non pharmacologic measures.

No particular class of antihypertensive drugs has been shown to be superior to another class in terms of their effects in children. The choice of antihypertensive agent depends on the underlying cause e.g. in post streptococcal glomerulonephritis, diuretics are the preferred agents, since hypertension is secondary to salt and water retention. When choosing the available therapies, the clinician must also consider efficacy, dosing availability and frequency, adverse effects and cost. It is easier to dose amlodipine in children, as it is water soluble and stable as a suspension as opposed to nifedipine. Angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitors (ACEI) and angiotensin receptor blockers have assumed increasing popularity in recent times in view of their advantages of reducing proteinuria and retarding the progression of renal disease, an effect independent of their antihypertensive effect. The target blood pressure goal for children with uncomplicated primary hypertension and no hypertensive target-organ damage, should be <95th percentile for gender, age and height. For children with chronic renal disease, diabetes, or hypertensive target-organ damage, the goal BP should be <90th percentile for gender, age, and height.

Drugs for Hypertensive Children

Drug		Dose initial	Maximum
Hypertensive emergencies	Nifedipine	0.25 mg/kg	0.5 mg/kg
	Sodium nitroprusside	0.5 µg/kg/min IV	8 µg/kg/min IV
	Labetalol	1 mg/kg/hr IV,	3 mg/kg/hr IV
Long-term therapy	Captopril	Neonates	0.03 mg/kg/d
		Children	1.5 mg/kg/d
	Enalapril	0.15 mg/kg/d	0.6 mg/kg/d
	Losartan	0.7 mg/kg/d	1.4 mg/kg/d

	Extended-release nifedipine	0.25 mg/kg/d	3 mg/kg/d
	Amlodipine	0.1 mg/kg/d	0.6 mg/kg/d
	Propranolol	1 mg/kg/d	8 mg/kg/d
	Atenolol	1 mg/kg/d	8 mg/kg/d
	Prazosin	0.05-0.1 mg/kg/d	0.5 mg/kg/d
	Minoxidil	0.1-0.2 mg/kg/d	1 mg/kg/d
	Hydrochlorothiazide	1 mg/kg/d	2-3 mg/kg/d
	Furosemide	1 mg/kg/d	12 mg/kg/d

Evaluation

The extent of the evaluation depends on the age of the child, the severity of the hypertension, the extent of end-organ damage, and the long-term risk factors for the individual patient. Children with blood pressure levels >90th percentile have 2.4 times the risk of hypertension in adulthood, compared to those with levels <90th percentile.

Initial evaluation

This needs to be performed by the general pediatrician. A thorough personal and family history and physical examination is followed by urine dipstick exam and baseline chemistry. An abdominal ultrasound is a useful screening investigation, which evaluates the size of the kidneys, detects tumors of the adrenal gland and the kidneys and is valuable in the diagnosis of cystic renal diseases, renal calculi, dilatation of the collecting system, or of duplex system, ureterocele, and thickened bladder wall.

Additional evaluation

All children with hypertension need a nephrology consult for additional evaluation as by definition, essential hypertension is a diagnosis of exclusion. All children with history of UTI should undergo a ⁹⁹Tc dimercaptosuccinic acid static scan. This is more sensitive than conventional intravenous urography, requires less exposure to radiation and is considered the gold standard for diagnosis of renal scarring. A furosemide DTPA scan is helpful when an obstructive uropathy is suspected (Table II). An MCU is recommended in children under 2 years of age with history of UTI to diagnose and stage the degree of reflux and plan further management.

Target end organ damage

The evaluation of hypertensive children should include assessment for additional risk factors. These risk factors include low plasma high-density lipoprotein cholesterol, elevated plasma triglyceride and abnormal glucose tolerance. If there is a strong family history of diabetes, a

hemoglobin A1C or glucose tolerance test may be considered especially in adolescents. An echocardiography is recommended to evaluate for evidence of LVH.

Evaluation of Child with Hypertension Level I (Initial evaluation)

- Full blood count
- Serum electrolytes, uric acid, renal function tests, lipid profile
- Urinalysis, culture.
- Renal ultrasound

Level II (Additional tests as indicated)

- Echocardiography
- Nuclear scans - DMSA, captopril renography, DTPA diuretic scan
- Doppler ultrasound of renal arteries
- Serum T3, T4, TSH
- Urinary catecholamines
- Plasma aldosterone and plasma renin activity, urine steroids
- MIBG scan
- Renal arteriography/DSA (after urinary catecholamines exclude pheochromocytoma).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The prevalence of hypertension is growing on day by day. Both Primary and Secondary hypertension are directly or indirectly related with food habits, sedentary life styles and consumption of various drugs. The antihypertensive drugs are classified as according to their site of action, their target organ receptors and their mode of actions. Older drugs for hypertension are outdated due to their various side effects and newer are going on to be incorporated in treatment schedule. All types of antihypertensive drugs are only able to do symptomatic decrease in blood pressure. They are not able to treat the real cause of hypertension. Hypertensive complications manifested as end organ damage are the major indicator of advanced disease. The timing of appearance of organ damage was dependent on the presence of triggering factors. This study aimed to evaluate the burden and determinants of total organ damage in hypertensive patients.

This study collects important information related to the Dietary Approaches to Stop Hypertension (DASH) pattern its positive effects on BP, overweight, and obesity in

adolescents. Hypertension is one of the most common diseases in the world. Recognition of hypertension is often difficult because most patients have no symptoms and diagnosis relies on routine blood pressure measurements. Control of blood pressure requires complex integration of regulatory mechanisms across multiple physiological systems. A sustained increase in arterial pressure therefore reflects a failure of one or more of these controls. The goal of therapy is to prevent end organ damage and reduce overall cardiovascular risk in the population. Searching for a secondary cause of hypertension is important because treating the underlying cause may alleviate the hypertension and avoid the need for long term antihypertensive medicines. Lifestyle modifications are effective in reducing blood pressure and they enhance pharmacological therapy.

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